

Dragonfly and Damselfly Diversity in Kanger Valley National Park, Bastar , Chhattisgarh

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Vinod Kumar Soni

Associate Professor
SOS Forestry & Wildlife
Shaheed Mahendra Karma
Vishwavidyalaya
Jagdalpur,CG, India

Namita Guha

Student
SOS Forestry & Wildlife
Shaheed Mahendra Karma
Vishwavidyalaya
Jagdalpur, CG, India

Abstract

The present investigation was carried out in Kanger Valley National Park (KVNP) ,Bastar district of Chhattisgarh during the month of April 2023 to June 2023. The study deals with the identification of species diversity and habitat of dragonfly and damselfly belonging to the order Odonata and they are collectively called Odonates. Odonates are responsive to changes in ecosystems, atmospheric temperature and weather conditions and also act as indicators of climate change. The research was conducted on using random walk and transect walk methods and survey was done at different habitats in Park areas (KVNP).

A total of 34 species of dragonflies are found at KVNP belonging to 08 families. Out of 34 species, 22 species of dragonflies species and 12 damselflies were recorded at various habitats like grasslands, river site and forest floor. During the survey, a total of 16 species are common, 13 species are uncommon and remaining 05 species are rare in the KVNP. As far as the IUCN red list is concerned and all the 34 species are recorded under the 'Least Concern'. The present research works are useful for the identification and documentation of dragonfly and damselfly species and their role in bioindicators of balance forests ecosystem.

The conservation of the natural habitat of the dragonflies and damselflies are necessary and urgent need to the further research on the role of these dragonflies and damselflies species to enhance the productivity of forests and an ecosystem.

Keywords

Kanger, Dragonfly , Damselfly, Odonates , Habitat, Forests Etc.

Introduction

Chhattisgarh is the state of India lies in (17.783 to 24.1°N and 80.25 to 84.4°E) with an area of 1,35,198 sq. km, out of which 44% is forested. Chhattisgarh is one of the most heavily forested States in India. The eight forest types according to the classification (Champion and Seth, 1968), together with a variety of non-forest habitats, harbours rich biodiversity. Biogeographically, Chhattisgarh straddles the central highlands of India and the Eastern Ghats.

The present investigation on the " Odonata" or often known as a dragonfly, has never been done in the environment of Kanger Valley National Park. Dragonflies and Damselflies are generally belonging to the order " Odonata", so they are collectively called Odonates, are one of the most common insects flying over forest, fields, meadows, ponds, and rivers (Thomas *et al* , 2018).

Objective of study

The present study was conducted to survey and identification of diversity of odonates (Dragonflies and Damselflies) and their different habitat in Kanger Valley National Park, Bastar district of Chhattisgarh.

Review of Literature

Odonata constitute a small well-known order of insects that are widely distributed over the world. Odonata has three sub- orders i.e., Anisoptera, Anisozygoptera and Zygoptera.

(Anisoptera) known as dragonfly and (Zygoptera) known as the damselfly. The Anisozygoptera represented by one species one species in India which is endangered in nature. There are mainly four families in order Anisoptera Family: **Gomphidae, Ashenidae, Cordulegasteridae, Libellulidae**. Approximately 6000 species and subspecies to 630 genera in 28 families are known from all over the world, out of this 6000 species and subspecies, 499 species and subspecies of odonata under 139 genera in 17 families are represented in India. It is closely linked with water bodies. The order odonata is one of the ancient groups of insects. These magnificent insects have been around from the carboniferous era about 250 million years ago (Kumar *et al*, 2018).

Odonates are responsive to changes in ecosystems, atmospheric temperature, and weather conditions, making them strong indicators of environmental changes. Odonata present in all kinds of habitats along the habitat permanent gradient ranging from permanent running waters and lakes to small temporary rain pools. Odonata present in all kinds of habitats along the habitat permanent gradient ranging from permanent running waters and lakes to small temporary rain pools (Supanekar *et al*, 2021).

Methodology

The Kanger Valley National Park is geographically situated on the south east of the Jagdalpur city in Bastar division. The geographic coordinates of national park is latitude (18°45'00"N to 18°56'30"N) and longitude (81°5'30"E to 82°10' 00"E). It is covered by mixed moist deciduous type of forests and water bodies. It spans an area of 200 sq km in Bastar division. The KVNP consists of hilly terrain and the park derives its name from the Kanger River, which flows throughout its length. History of the Kanger Valley National Parks dates back to the year 1982. The government of Chhattisgarh declared the forests spread on the south east of Jagdalpur as KangerValley National Park in the year 1982 to protect different species of flora and fauna living in the Bastar division of Chhattisgarh. The floral diversity of the park is considered as in-situ gene bank of medicinal plants, grasses, climbers, wild sugarcane, Bamboo species, canes, ferns, epiphytes, Sal, Teak, and their rich associates along with the species of Sal and Teak trees.

The study was undertaken during the months of March 2023 to June 2023. The methodology of the research work was based on Random walk method and Transect walk method. The selection of methods for survey was depending upon the dragonfly habitat in Kanger Valley National Park. All the species that come across were photographed in the fields during survey periods. we have used Nikon D3200 DSLR camera to capture pictures of dragonflies and damselflies species in and around the study sites. iPhone XR was also used for capturing the pictures of dragonflies and damselflies and it are used for GPS tracking.

Result and Discussion

In the present study, a total of 34 species of dragonflies and damselflies recorded from Kanger Valley National Park , during the study period from March-June 2023, out of total count, sub-order Anisoptera (Dragonflies) accounts for 22 species while sub-order Zygoptera (Damselflies) accounts for remaining 12 species. The 21 species of the sub-order Anisoptera is distributed into 3 families viz, Libellulidae with 16 species, Aeshnidae with 4 species and Gomphidae with 1 species while those of 12 species of the sub-order zygoptera is distributed under 5 families viz, Coenagrionidae with 6 species, Chlorocyphidae with 2 species, Calopterygidae with 1 species, Platycnemididae with 2 species and Protoneuridae with 1 species (Table 1&2).

In terms of species number, the family **Libellulidae** was found to be most dominant contributing 17 species to the total count of odonates which are supported by a various similar studies (Choudhury *et al*. 2020; Tiple and Chandra ,2013; Manwar *et al*.2014; Koneri *et al*. 2022; Bora, 2019). During the present study, a total number of 16 species are common, 13 are uncommon and remaining 5 species are rare to the study area. As far as the IUCN Red List is concerned. All the 34 species recorded are under the least concern categories. A review of the past works revealed that Choudhury *et al*. (2020) reported that total 57 species of odonate from 39 genera and 8 families at Chakrashila Wildlife Sanctuary of western, Assam. In a similar study Patil *et, al* (2018) reported total 719 individuals of odonates belonging to 06 families, 23 genera and 34 species of odonate in Khanapur Tehsil Dist. Sangli (M.S.), India. A total of 16 species of odonates belonging to 12 genera and 5 families were recorded by Athira and Dhivya (2021) in Kannur and Wayanad district of Kerala,

The habitat assessment of odonates was also surveyed and the suitable natural habitat condition are profound available found in the tropical moist deciduous forests. The habitats components are profound available for both the 34 species dragonflies & damselflies in Kanger Valley National Park, Chhattisgarh.

The present study indicated the presence of divers species of dragonflies and damselflies of Kanger Valley National Park , Chhattisgarh while majority of dominant species are belonging to family Libellulidae and that was found to be most dominant of insect

family contributing 17 species to the total count of odonates. During present study, a total of 16 species are common, 13 are uncommon and remaining 5 species are rare to the study area. As far as the IUCN red list is concerned, all the 34 species recorded are under the category least concern.

Table 1: Preliminary Checklist of Dragonflies and their natural habitat in KVNP

Sl.No	Scientific Names	Common Names	Habitats	Visual Abundance	IUCN Status
Sub-order : Anisoptera Family:-Gomphidae					
1	<i>Ictinogomphus rapax</i>	Common clubtail	GL	C	LC
Family :- Libellulidae					
2	<i>Orthetrum pruinosum</i>	Crimson-Tailed Marsh Hawk	R,TT	C	LC
3	<i>Bradinopyga geminate</i>	Granite Ghost	R	C	LC
4	<i>Neurothemis fulvia</i>	Fulvous Forest Skimmer	PT	R	LC
5	<i>Trithemis aurora</i>	Crimson Marsh Glider	R,PT	C	LC
6	<i>Trithemis festiva</i>	Black Stream Glider	L,PT,GL	C	LC
7	<i>Pachydiplax longipennis</i>	Blue Dasher	PT	UC	LC
8	<i>Diplacodes trivialis</i>	Ground Skimmer	R,DL,L	C	LC
9	<i>Crocothemis servilia</i>	Scarlet Skimmer	GL,PT	C	LC
10	<i>Neurothemis intermedia</i>	Ruddy Meadow Skimmer	PT	C	LC
11	<i>Rhyothemis variegata</i>	Common Picture Wing	PT,L	UC	LC
12	<i>Cratillalineata</i>	Emerald-Banded Skimmer	PT	UC	LC
13	<i>Lathrecista asiatica</i>	Asiatic Blood Tail	PT	UC	LC
14	<i>Orthetrum Glaucum</i>	Blue Marsh Hawk	R,PT	C	LC
15	<i>Erythrodiplax umbrata</i>	Band-Winged Dragonlet	PT	UC	LC
16	<i>Orthetrum Sabina</i>	Slender Skimmer	PT	UC	LC
17	<i>Brachythemis contaminata</i>	Ditch Jewel	PT,WB	C	LC
18	<i>Tholymistilla</i>	Crepuscular darter	WB, PT	UC	LC
Family :- Aeshnidae					
19	<i>Anax parthenope</i>	The Lesser Emperor	R	R	LC
20	<i>Anax indicus</i>	Elephant Emperor	PT	UC	LC
21	<i>Gynacantha saltatrix</i>	Little Dusk- Hawker	R	R	LC
22	<i>Gynacantha bayadera</i>	Parakeet Darner	PT	C	LC